

Photoinduced transformation pathways of the sulfonamide antibiotic sulfamethoxazole, relevant to sunlit surface waters[☆]

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Sulfamethoxazole
Photodegradation
Transformation products
Natural water matrices
UV-B radiation

ABSTRACT

Here we report that sulfamethoxazole (SMZ) is expected to undergo photodegradation in sunlit surface waters, due to direct photolysis and indirect photochemistry. The direct photolysis of SMZ is triggered by absorption of UV-B radiation and is mostly relevant to shallow water bodies, where a non-negligible part of the water column is illuminated by short-wavelength radiation. In deeper water layers, where the UV-B intensity is much lower, indirect photochemistry processes could take on importance. In particular, upon irradiation of natural water samples, we got evidence that triplet-sensitized degradation of SMZ might be an important or even the main reaction pathway in brackish-water environments, in the presence of elevated concentrations of humic substances. The direct UV-B photolysis of SMZ would produce transformation products that are comparably toxic or less toxic than SMZ itself, thereby resulting in overall decontamination. In contrast, longer-wavelength ($\lambda > 340$ nm) irradiation of SMZ in natural water matrices could produce a potentially toxic compound.

1. Introduction

Sulfamethoxazole (SMZ) is a synthetic sulfonamide antibiotic used in human and veterinary medicine, including aquaculture, to combat bacterial infections (Du and Liu, 2012; Zhang et al., 2013). The widespread application of SMZ has led to its frequent detection in various environmental matrices, such as surface waters, sediments, and soils (Wang et al., 2024). The primary pathways through which SMZ enters the environment include the excretion of non-metabolized drug residues by humans and animals, discharge from wastewater treatment plants, and runoff from agricultural and aquaculture activities (Sanusi et al., 2023). According to Wang and Wang (2018), the conventional wastewater treatment processes often exhibit limited efficiency in removing SMZ, leading to its continuous release into aquatic systems.

In aquaculture, SMZ is administered to prevent and treat bacterial diseases in aquatic organisms (Masters et al., 2003). However, its use raises environmental concerns due to the potential development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and the persistence of SMZ in aquatic ecosystems (Sanusi et al., 2023). Studies have shown that SMZ can also adversely affect non-target aquatic species, including commercially important ones like *Litopenaeus vannamei* (whiteleg shrimp), of which SMZ decreases growth performance and immune functions and alters

the gut microbiota (Chen et al., 2023).

Once introduced into the environment, SMZ undergoes various transformation processes such as photodegradation and biodegradation (Reis et al., 2014). Environmental factors like pH, temperature, and organic matter can affect the degradation of SMZ. For example, according to Wang et al. (2024), acidic conditions can change the vertical migration of SMZ in soil and affect its environmental fate. Also, according to Zhang et al. (2023), SMZ can be adsorbed onto microplastics in aquatic environments, which may serve as vectors for its transport and affect bioavailability.

The photoinduced transformation processes in sunlit surface waters encompass both direct photolysis and indirect photochemistry. The direct photolysis is triggered by absorption of sunlight by the contaminants, which induces their transformation via bond breaking, electron transfer, excited-state reactions, and so on (Liang et al., 2022; Yuan et al., 2020). In the case of indirect photochemistry, sunlight is absorbed by natural photosensitizers (especially nitrate NO_3^- , nitrite NO_2^- , and chromophoric dissolved organic matter CDOM) to generate the so-called photochemically produced reactive intermediates (PPRIs). These PPRIs are short-lived species that include hydroxyl ($^{\bullet}\text{OH}$) and carbonate ($\text{CO}_3^{\bullet-}$) radicals, singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$), and CDOM triplet states ($^3\text{CDOM}^*$). The PPRIs react with the contaminants and induce their transformation (Guo

[☆] This paper has been recommended for acceptance by Klaus Kümmerer.

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et al., 2023). In the case of SMZ, previous studies based on laboratory experiments have identified direct photolysis as the most important transformation pathway. There are reports for the process to be quite fast (Oliveira et al., 2019), moderately fast (Trovó et al., 2009), or rather slow (Boreen et al., 2004), presumably depending on differences in irradiation conditions. Furthermore, indirect photodegradation of SMZ might be important in some circumstances (Ryan et al., 2011; Bahn-müller et al., 2014).

The present work has the goal of combining irradiation experiments and photochemical modeling to conclusively assess the persistence and fate of SMZ in sunlit surface-water environments. Understanding the occurrence, fate, and ecological impact of SMZ is in fact crucial for developing effective management strategies that may mitigate its environmental presence and associated risks.

Previous works have studied the photodegradation mechanisms of SMZ in synthetic or freshwater systems (e.g., Boreen et al., 2004), but the present study presents a novel examination of the role of triplet-sensitized reactions in real aquaculture environments. The use of brackish water high in DOC and humic signature allowed examination of $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ -mediated processes, which was supported by 2,4,6-trimethylphenol probe experiments. In addition, we have identified photo-transformation intermediates formed under different conditions, assessing their potential toxicity with *in silico* tools.

This work adds new knowledge to prior studies of SMZ photodegradation. Unlike earlier research that employed ultra-pure or synthetic natural water, here we used real environmental water matrices, including aquaculture pond water, to capture the complexity of natural conditions. This integration connects controlled experiments with real-case environmental scenarios, allowing for an assessment of SMZ fate under different real conditions and for a validation of those predictions with real data.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Reagents and materials

Sulfamethoxazole (SMZ, purity grade 99 %), paracetamol (APAP, purity grade 98 %), sodium nitrate (NaNO_3 , >99 %), sodium hydrogen carbonate (NaHCO_3 , 98 %), 2-nitrobenzaldehyde (2-NBA, 98 %), 2,4,6-trimethylphenol (TMP or $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, purity grade >97 %), and 4-carboxybenzophenone (CBBP, purity grade 99 %) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Rose Bengal (RB) from Alfa Aesar. Phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4 , 86 %) was purchased from VWR Chemicals.

2.2. Irradiation experiments

In preparation of the irradiation experiments, 5 mL of solutions were introduced into cylindrical Pyrex glass cells (4.0 cm diameter, 2.4 cm height) that were then placed under each relevant lamp (*vide infra*). The cells were closed with a lateral screw cap and magnetically stirred during irradiation. After the scheduled irradiation time, 1 mL of the solution was transferred to an HPLC vial for analysis by liquid chromatography (*vide infra*).

In surface waters, the main photodegradation processes are usually the direct photolysis and the reactions with $\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$, $^1\text{O}_2$, and the triplet states $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ (De Laurentiis et al., 2014). Such processes were studied with specific photosensitizers, irradiated under lamps that selectively excited them. In particular, $\cdot\text{OH}$ was generated by nitrate under UV-B irradiation, $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ by nitrate + bicarbonate under UV-B irradiation, triplet states by UV-A irradiation of CBBP, used as representative triplet sensitizer, and $^1\text{O}_2$ by irradiation of the dye Rose Bengal under a yellow lamp. More specifically, the direct photolysis of SMZ was studied by irradiating SMZ alone under a Philips Narrowband TL 20 W/01RS UV-B lamp. The same lamp was used to irradiate SMZ + nitrate (reaction with $\cdot\text{OH}$) and SMZ + nitrate + bicarbonate (reaction with $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$) (De Laurentiis et al., 2014). Spectral output and light source

intensities were monitored using both a CO.FO.ME.GRA power meter and chemical actinometry, following published methods (Allen et al., 2000), to allow for the calibration of irradiation conditions. The UV-B lamp had $3.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ irradiance in the UV range (280–400 nm), measured with the mentioned power meter. Chemical actinometry measurements were based on the photoisomerization of 2-NBA into 2-nitrosobenzoic acid. In a Pyrex cell, $10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ solutions of 2-NBA were irradiated for up to 6 min, monitoring the degradation of 2-NBA by liquid chromatography and calculating the absorbed photon flux, P_a , based on the known photolysis quantum yield ($\Phi_{2\text{-NBA}} = 0.4$; $P_a = R_{2\text{-NBA}} (\Phi_{2\text{-NBA}})^{-1}$, where $R_{2\text{-NBA}}$ is the initial degradation rate of 2-NBA; Allen et al., 2000).

To assess the reactivity between SMZ and $^3\text{CDOM}^*$, CBBP was used as a CDOM proxy because the triplet state of CBBP ($^3\text{CBBP}^*$) has comparable reactivity to typical CDOM triplet states ($^3\text{CDOM}^*$), thereby providing reasonable second-order rate constants for reactions with contaminants (Carena et al., 2019). The photodegradation of SMZ sensitized by CBBP was studied using a 16 W Philips TL-D Black UV-A lamp, with $23 \pm 2 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ UV irradiance. The SMZ transformation photosensitized by Rose Bengal via $^1\text{O}_2$ was studied under a TL D 18W/16 yellow lamp, with an emission maximum at 545 nm and $11 \pm 1 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ irradiance in the visible. The three light sources were selected to selectively activate the different photochemical pathways, relevant to natural sunlight scenarios. The UV-B lamp (Philips TL 20 W/01RS) was used to simulate short-wavelength solar radiation inducing direct photolysis of SMZ. The UV-A lamp (Philips TL-D Black 16 W) was selected to excite $^3\text{CBBP}^*$, allowing assessment of $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ -induced reactions. The yellow lamp (Philips TL-D 18W/16) was used to activate Rose Bengal for the generation of $^1\text{O}_2$, avoiding SMZ excitation. These lamps are different in their emission maxima, irradiance, and spectral overlap with SMZ and sensitizers. These differences determine the relative contributions of direct vs. sensitized phototransformation pathways, ensuring pathway-specific degradation assessments.

2.3. Competition kinetics between SMZ and APAP

The second-order reaction rate constants of SMZ with PPRIs ($\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$, $^1\text{O}_2$, and $^3\text{CBBP}^*$) were determined by competition kinetics between SMZ itself and paracetamol (APAP), where the latter was chosen as reference compound of known reactivity (Carena et al., 2019; De Laurentiis et al., 2014). The competition kinetics method is based on the monitoring of the time evolution of SMZ and APAP that occur together in the same solution, where they are both exposed to the same steady-state concentration of the relevant PPRI ($\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$, $^3\text{CBBP}^*$, or $^1\text{O}_2$) produced by each photosensitizer (respectively, nitrate, nitrate + bicarbonate, CBBP, or Rose Bengal) (Minella et al., 2017). The reaction rate constant of SMZ with $\cdot\text{OH}$ was determined upon UV-B irradiation of SMZ + APAP + nitrate, that with $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ upon UV-B irradiation of SMZ + APAP + nitrate + bicarbonate. The NaHCO_3 was added to promote the formation of carbonate radicals ($\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$) from hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$), allowing for the assessment of SMZ reactivity with $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ as described by De Laurentiis et al. (2014). The reaction rate constant of SMZ with $^3\text{CBBP}^*$ was determined by irradiating SMZ + APAP + CBBP under the UV-A lamp, that with $^1\text{O}_2$ by irradiation of SMZ + APAP + Rose Bengal under the yellow lamp. Wherever relevant, the initial concentration values were as follows: 5 μM SMZ, 5 μM APAP, 1 mM NaNO_3 , 1 M NaHCO_3 , 70 μM CBBP, 10 μM Rose Bengal. The high value of the NaHCO_3 concentration was motivated by the need to ensure that practically all $\cdot\text{OH}$ photogenerated by nitrate photolysis reacted with $\text{HCO}_3^-/\text{CO}_3^{2-}$ to produce $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$, at the same time minimizing the side reaction between SMZ/APAP and $\cdot\text{OH}$.

Considering that APAP and, most notably, SMZ would undergo direct photolysis under UV-B and short UV-A irradiation, the observed photodegradation in the presence of each photosensitizer would result from both direct phototransformation and reaction with the relevant PPRI. Therefore, to assess the contribution of direct photolysis, blank

experiments were also carried out by irradiating 5 μM SMZ and 5 μM APAP without photosensitizers, under, respectively: (i) UV-B lamp; (ii) UV-B lamp in the presence of 1 M NaHCO_3 , and (iii) UV-A lamp.

take these issues into account, correction of k'_{SMZ} and k'_{APAP} for SMZ and APAP direct photolysis was carried out as follows (PPRI = $\bullet\text{OH}$, $\text{CO}_3^{\bullet-}$, or $^3\text{CBBP}^*$; Sens = nitrate or CBBP) (Carena et al., 2019):

$$(k')_{\text{SMZ,PPRI}} = k'_{\text{SMZ}} - k'_{\text{d.p.,SMZ}} \frac{\int_{\lambda} \frac{\epsilon_{\text{SMZ}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,SMZ}}}{C_{\text{O,SMZ}} + \epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}} + \epsilon_{\text{Sens}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,Sens}}} P^{\circ}(\lambda) \{1 - 10^{-b[\epsilon_{\text{SMZ}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,SMZ}} + \epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}} + \epsilon_{\text{Sens}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,Sens}}]}\} d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda} \frac{\epsilon_{\text{SMZ}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,SMZ}}}{C_{\text{O,SMZ}} + \epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}}} P^{\circ}(\lambda) \{1 - 10^{-b[\epsilon_{\text{SMZ}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,SMZ}} + \epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}}]}\} d\lambda} \quad (2)$$

$$(k')_{\text{APAP,PPRI}} = k'_{\text{APAP}} - k'_{\text{d.p.,APAP}} \frac{\int_{\lambda} \frac{\epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}}}{C_{\text{O,SMZ}} + \epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}} + \epsilon_{\text{Sens}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,Sens}}} P^{\circ}(\lambda) \{1 - 10^{-b[\epsilon_{\text{SMZ}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,SMZ}} + \epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}} + \epsilon_{\text{Sens}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,Sens}}]}\} d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda} \frac{\epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}}}{C_{\text{O,SMZ}} + \epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}}} P^{\circ}(\lambda) \{1 - 10^{-b[\epsilon_{\text{SMZ}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,SMZ}} + \epsilon_{\text{APAP}}(\lambda) C_{\text{O,APAP}}]}\} d\lambda} \quad (3)$$

2.4. Experiments with natural water matrices

Description of sampling and sample treatment procedures, irradiation experiments, and measurement of anions, dissolved organic carbon (DOC), pH, and sample fluorescence are reported in the Supplementary Material (SM), **Text SM1**.

2.5. Absorbance and liquid chromatography measurements

The absorption spectra of the compounds to be irradiated (SMZ, APAP, 2-NBA) were measured with a double-beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 100 Scan), using quartz cuvettes with 1 cm optical path length.

The time trends of SMZ and APAP were monitored by HPLC-UV/vis, using a YL9300 HPLC System (Young Lin, S. Korea) equipped with a UV/vis detector, YL9150 Autosampler, and YL-9330 column compartment housing a LichroCART - Lichrospher 100 RP-18 column (Merck, 125 mm \times 4 mm \times 5 μm). The SMZ and APAP were eluted with a mixture of 4.5 mmol L^{-1} H_3PO_4 in water (A) and acetonitrile (B), with a total flow rate of 1 mL min^{-1} . The following conditions were used (λ = detection wavelength, t_{R} = retention time) in the different systems.

- (i) The SMZ alone. Isocratic elution (65 % A, 35 % B), λ = 263 nm, t_{R} = 2.8 min.
- (ii) The mixture SMZ + APAP. Gradient elution: initially 10 % B, up to 30 % B in 5 min, keep for 10 min, down to 10 % B in 5 min. APAP: λ = 245 nm, t_{R} = 2.2 min. SMZ: λ = 263 nm, t_{R} = 8.7 min.

2.6. Kinetic data treatment

The direct photolysis of SMZ followed pseudo-first-order kinetics, and the relevant time trends were fitted using the following equation:

$$C_t = C_0 \exp(-k' t) \quad (1)$$

where C_t is the substrate concentration at the irradiation time t , C_0 the initial concentration, and k' the pseudo-first order degradation rate constant.

In the case of competition kinetics experiments (SMZ + APAP + photosensitizer, where photosensitizer = nitrate, nitrate + bicarbonate, or CBBP), first of all, the first-order photodegradation rate constants of SMZ (k'_{SMZ}) and APAP (k'_{APAP}) were determined with equation (1). As mentioned in Section 2.3, these k' values would derive from both direct photolysis and PPRI reaction. Direct photolysis kinetics are provided by blank experiments (irradiation of SMZ + APAP without photosensitizers) that return the first-order rate coefficients $k'_{\text{d.p.,SMZ}}$ and $k'_{\text{d.p.,APAP}}$, respectively. In the presence of photosensitizers (nitrate, nitrate + bicarbonate, CBBP), there is competition for lamp irradiance among SMZ, APAP, and nitrate or CBBP, which slows down the direct photolysis of both SMZ and APAP compared to the absence of photosensitizers. To

where the ratios between the integrals represent the ratios between the photon fluxes absorbed by SMZ (equation (2)) or APAP (equation (3)) in the ternary mixture (SMZ + APAP + nitrate or CBBP) vs. the binary one (SMZ + APAP). By so doing, the values of $(k')_{\text{SMZ,PPRI}}$ and $(k')_{\text{APAP,PPRI}}$ thus obtained are the first-order rate coefficients referred to the actual reactions of the two compounds with PPRI = $\bullet\text{OH}$, $\text{CO}_3^{\bullet-}$, or $^3\text{CBBP}^*$, which exclude the contribution of the direct photolysis. There was no need to make similar corrections for Rose Bengal, because neither SMZ nor APAP absorb yellow light.

On this basis, the second-order reaction rate constant of SMZ with each relevant PPRI ($k''_{\text{SMZ} + \text{PPRI}}$) was calculated as follows:

$$k''_{\text{SMZ} + \text{PPRI}} = k''_{\text{APAP} + \text{PPRI}} (k')_{\text{SMZ,PPRI}} [(k')_{\text{APAP,PPRI}}]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where $k''_{\text{APAP} + \text{PPRI}}$ is the known second-order reaction rate constant of APAP with each relevant PPRI (Carena et al., 2019; De Laurentiis et al., 2014).

2.7. Photochemical modeling

The photodegradation of SMZ was modeled with the software APEX (Aquatic Photochemistry of Environmental Xenobiotics; Vione, 2020). The software APEX predicts half-life times and photodegradation rate coefficients of contaminants, referred to a clear-sky scenario corresponding to the 15th of July at 45°N latitude (total UV dose of 7.9×10^5 J m^{-2} ; Bodrato and Vione, 2014). The software uses as input data the bimolecular reaction rate constants of indirect photodegradation, as well as the absorption spectrum and direct photolysis quantum yield of the investigated contaminant (SMZ in the present case). The software also needs environmental data of water depth and water chemistry; moreover, monthly trends of photodegradation kinetics can be obtained with the *APEX_season* function. The APEX model simulations were configured using a water column depth of 3 m, and inorganic constituent concentrations were set at 10^{-4} M NO_3^- , 10^{-6} M NO_2^- , 10^{-3} M HCO_3^- , and 10^{-5} M CO_3^{2-} , to represent reasonable aquaculture water conditions. The DOC concentrations were varied up to 20 $\text{mg}_C \text{L}^{-1}$, to encompass conditions found in the investigated water samples (see **Table SM1**).

2.8. Identification of the transformation products (TPs) of SMZ

A volume of 5 mL and same irradiation conditions described in Section 2.2 (fluorescent lamps) and in **Text SM1** (solar simulator) were used to determine the TPs of SMZ. To do so, 1 mL sample aliquots were collected at scheduled times and analyzed by liquid chromatography – mass spectrometry, using a Shimadzu UPLC instrument combined with a 3200 QTRAP LC-MS/MS system from SCIEX (Framingham, MA, USA).

First, a full scan was performed in positive Enhanced MS Scan mode with a mass range of 50–350 m/z . The ion source parameters were as follows: temperature (TEM) 600 °C; ion spray floating voltage (ISFV)

4500 V; curtain gas (CUR) 30 L min⁻¹; ion source gases (GS1 and GS2) both 20 psi. Chromatographic separation was carried out on a Kinetex 3.5 μm PAH column. The flow rate was set to 0.5 mL min⁻¹, using 0.1 % formic acid (A) and methanol (B) as mobile phases. The percentage of B was changed linearly as follows: 0–10 min at 10 % B, up to 100 % B in 7 min, down to 10 % in 0.1 min, and keep it until completing 25 min of total run. The declustering potential (DP) was 20 V, collision energy (CE) was 10 eV, and the entrance potential was set to 10 V. For the acquisition of MS/MS data, enhanced product ion scan (EPI) was used with the following parameters: temperature (TEM) 450 °C; ion spray floating voltage (ISVF) 4500 V; curtain gas (CUR) 35 L min⁻¹; ion source gases (GS1 and GS2) 45 psi and 55 psi, respectively. The declustering potential (DP) was 20 V, collision energy (CE) 10 eV, and the entrance potential was set to 10 V.

2.9. Toxicity assessments

The possible environmental effects of the TPs detected in this work, compared to SMZ, were assessed by means of the Ecological Structure Activity Relationships (ECOSAR) Predictive Model software, version 2.2 (United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)). In particular, we selected the values for the worst toxicity case scenario. The ECOSAR determines three endpoints, namely: (i) LC₅₀ (Lethal concentration 50 %), which represents the concentration expected to be lethal for 50 % of the tested organisms; (ii) EC₅₀ (Effective Concentration 50 %), which is the concentration at which 50 % of the organisms show a specified effect, such as interruption of growth, and (iii) Chronic Values (ChV), which represent the geometric mean of the No-Observed-Effect Concentration (NOEC) and Lowest-Observed-Effect Concentration (LOEC). These values (mg L⁻¹) are calculated for fish (LC₅₀, ChV), daphnid (LC₅₀, ChV), and green algae (EC₅₀, ChV). The lower is the toxicity endpoint value, the more toxic is the relevant compound. The selected organisms (green algae, daphnid, and fish) represent standard taxa for aquatic ecotoxicity testing, covering three trophic levels (primary producers, invertebrates, and vertebrates). ECOSAR is used to predict the toxicity to a general aquatic community and is aligned with OECD guidelines and regulatory frameworks (e.g., US EPA ECOSAR), which recommend these organisms for environmental risk assessment of the contaminants and their transformation products (Wright et al., 2022).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The SMZ photodegradation kinetics

Fig. 1a shows the results of preliminary survey experiments where 10 μM SMZ was irradiated in different conditions, including under the UV-B lamp: (i) SMZ alone to probe the direct photolysis; (ii) SMZ in the presence of 0.1 mM NaNO₃, to assess the reaction with •OH on top of the direct photolysis, and (iii) SMZ with 0.1 mM NaNO₃ + 1 M NaHCO₃. The addition of NaHCO₃ was intended to provide the HCO₃⁻ ions required to assess the reaction between SMZ and CO₃²⁻, the latter formed in the reactions involving •OH + HCO₃⁻ and •OH + CO₃²⁻. The SMZ was not detected in the studied natural water samples. Although the concentration of SMZ used in the experiments (10 μM) was higher than that found in the environment (range of ng/L or μg/L), it was in the range normally used in photochemical studies.

We were thus able to measure photolysis quantum yields and reaction rate constants, elucidate the mechanistic pathways, and detect TPs and their temporal evolution (Zhang et al., 2013; Sanusi et al., 2023; Boreen et al., 2004; Oliveira et al., 2019). The following reactions would take place in the nitrate-containing systems (reactions 6,7 occur in the presence of NaNO₃ + NaHCO₃; photogenerated •OH and CO₃²⁻ would then react with SMZ):

Fig. 1. (a) Time trends of preliminary SMZ experiments under different irradiation conditions. (b) Left Y-axis: absorption spectrum of SMZ (molar absorption coefficient $\epsilon_{\text{SMZ}}(\lambda)$). Right Y-axis: spectral photon flux density of the UV-B lamp in the irradiated solution ($p^\circ(\lambda)$). E = mol photons (Einstein).

Furthermore, 10 μM SMZ was also irradiated under the UV-A lamp in the presence of 70 μM CBBP, to assess the triplet-sensitized degradation involving ³CBBP*, and under the yellow lamp with 10 μM Rose Bengal to assess reaction with ¹O₂. The results (Fig. 1a) suggest that reaction with ¹O₂ would be negligible, while the other processes are potentially important. Also note that at the experimental pH value (pH 7), the prevailing form of SMZ (pK_a = 5.6; Palm et al., 2023) would be the anionic one that would also prevail in typical natural surface waters.

While UV-B irradiation of 10 μM SMZ alone is sufficient to determine the direct photolysis quantum yield (see section 3.1.1), the second-order reaction rate constants of SMZ with •OH, CO₃²⁻, and ³CBBP* were measured by competition kinetics with paracetamol (APAP) as reference compound (section 3.1.2). These data enable modeling of SMZ degradation kinetics and pathways, under general conditions that would be relevant to surface freshwaters (section 3.1.3).

3.1.1. Direct photolysis quantum yield of SMZ

The time evolution of 10 μM SMZ irradiated alone under the UV-B lamp could be fitted with the first-order equation (1). On this basis, the initial SMZ degradation rate is $R_{0,\text{SMZ}} = k'_{\text{SMZ}} C_{0,\text{SMZ}}$. The same rate can also be expressed as $R_{0,\text{SMZ}} = \Phi_{\text{SMZ}} P_{a,\text{SMZ}}$, where Φ_{SMZ} is the direct photolysis quantum yield of SMZ and $P_{a,\text{SMZ}}$ is the UV-B photon flux absorbed by SMZ (equation (8)).

$$P_{a,SMZ} = \int_{\lambda} p^{\circ}(\lambda) [1 - 10^{-\varepsilon_{SMZ}(\lambda) b C_{o,SMZ}}] d\lambda \quad (8)$$

In the equation, $p^{\circ}(\lambda)$ is the spectral photon flux density produced by the UV-B lamp inside the solution (units of $E L^{-1} s^{-1} nm^{-1}$, where $E = \text{Einstein} = \text{mol photons}$; see Fig. 1b) and $\varepsilon_{SMZ}(\lambda)$ is the molar absorption coefficient of SMZ (units of $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$, see Fig. 1b). Moreover, $b = 0.4 \text{ cm}$ is the optical path length of radiation in solution, and $C_{o,SMZ} = 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.

It was obtained $P_{a,SMZ} = 2.6 \times 10^{-8} E L^{-1} s^{-1}$ and, from the time trend of SMZ under UV-B irradiation, $R_{o,SMZ} = (7.58 \pm 0.31) \times 10^{-10} M s^{-1}$. From these data it was possible to calculate $\Phi_{SMZ} = R_{o,SMZ} (P_{a,SMZ})^{-1} = (2.91 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-2}$ as the direct photolysis quantum yield of SMZ. This value is in very good agreement with that reported by Palm et al. (2023) for anionic SMZ ($\Phi_{SMZ} = 0.03$).

3.1.2. Indirect photodegradation of SMZ

The second-order reaction rate constants of SMZ with $\bullet OH$, $CO_3^{\bullet -}$, and ${}^3CBPP^*$ (${}^3CDOM^*$ proxy) were measured by competition kinetics with APAP, which is a compound with known and significant reactivity towards the mentioned reactive transients. Note that, compared to the preliminary irradiation experiments, the concentration of $NaNO_3$ was here raised to 1 mM to enhance the $\bullet OH$ and $CO_3^{\bullet -}$ processes versus the direct photolysis. The values of $k_{APAP + PPRI}$ (Carena et al., 2019; De Laurentiis et al., 2014), as well as those of $k_{SMZ + PPRI}$ obtained with equations (2)–(4) are reported in Table 1. The reported standard deviation values were calculated from the error propagation of the fitting model. Interestingly, our value of $k_{SMZ + \bullet OH}$ compares very well with that reported by Sui et al. (2011) for the anionic form of SMZ.

3.1.3. Modeling of SMZ photodegradation

Using the absorption spectrum of SMZ (Fig. 1b), the measured value $\Phi_{SMZ} = 2.9 \times 10^{-2}$, and the second-order rate constants for reaction of SMZ with $\bullet OH$, $CO_3^{\bullet -}$, and ${}^3CBPP^*$ (${}^3CDOM^*$) reported in Table 1, it was possible to use the APEX software to model phototransformation kinetics in conditions that are representative of sunlit natural waters. On this basis, Figure SM1 in the Supplementary Material (SM) shows the predicted first-order photodegradation rate constants of SMZ (k_{SMZ}) and the corresponding half-life times ($t_{1/2} = \ln 2 (k_{SMZ})^{-1}$) as a function of the dissolved organic carbon (DOC), for a relatively shallow ($d = 3 \text{ m}$) freshwater body. Predictions are relevant to anionic SMZ, which would prevail in the majority of surface-water environments. In the hypothesized conditions, fair-weather summertime lifetimes would range between one day (low-DOC conditions) and one week (high-DOC conditions), thereby suggesting that SMZ is a quite photolabile compound. A year-round average prediction, obtained with the Apex-season function, foresees $t_{1/2} = 1 \text{ week}$ at mid latitude for $DOC = 3 \text{ mg}_C L^{-1}$. When using a range of 25 different molecules subject to comparable photochemical modeling as reference scale (Vione et al., 2024), SMZ would rank among the ‘fast photodegrading’ ones.

The direct photolysis would be the main SMZ photodegradation pathway in the modeled scenario (Figure SM1), while indirect photodegradation by $\bullet OH$, $CO_3^{\bullet -}$, and ${}^3CDOM^*$ would play secondary role. Inhibition of the direct photolysis by dissolved organic matter (competition for sunlight irradiance between SMZ and CDOM) mostly accounts for the decrease of k_{SMZ} with increasing DOC. As illustrated in

Table 1

Second-order reaction rate constants of APAP (reference compound; Carena et al., 2019; De Laurentiis et al., 2014) and anionic SMZ (this work) with $\bullet OH$, $CO_3^{\bullet -}$, and ${}^3CBPP^*$ (${}^3CDOM^*$ proxy). The error bounds represent $\pm\sigma$. Reaction between SMZ and 1O_2 was negligibly slow.

PPRI	$k_{APAP + PPRI}, M^{-1} s^{-1}$	$k_{SMZ + PPRI}, M^{-1} s^{-1}$
OH	$(1.87 \pm 0.56) \times 10^9$	$(2.73 \pm 1.11) \times 10^{10}$
$CO_3^{\bullet -}$	$(3.80 \pm 1.10) \times 10^8$	$(1.02 \pm 0.43) \times 10^8$
${}^3CBPP^*$	$(1.59 \pm 0.09) \times 10^9$	$(1.41 \pm 0.27) \times 10^8$

Figure SM1, the model shows an inverse relationship between DOC concentration and k_{SMZ} , suggesting that light screening is the dominant factor. This result is consistent with previous experimental findings by Oliveira et al. (2019). However, additional effects such as quenching of PPRIs by CDOM may also contribute marginally.

Note that SMZ direct photolysis is triggered by absorption of UV-B radiation (Fig. 1b), which only reaches the uppermost layers of surface waters (Vähätalo et al., 2005). In deeper environments, indirect photochemistry processes could become comparatively more important.

3.2. Photo-transformation of SMZ in natural water samples

The photochemical degradation of SMZ under simulated sunlight in natural water samples exhibited a different behavior than that observed in ultra-pure water, due to interactions with organic and inorganic compounds present in real environments. Moreover, the 340-nm cut-off filter would minimize radiation absorption by SMZ (Fig. 1b), thus minimizing the UV-B direct photolysis of the substrate. As mentioned above, irradiation with $\lambda > 340 \text{ nm}$ is suitable to assess the behavior of SMZ in rather deep natural water bodies. In all cases, the photodegradation of SMZ followed reasonable pseudo-first order kinetics. Table SM2 lists the values of the SMZ degradation rate constants observed in the different samples (k'_{SMZ} , obtained by data fit with equation (1)). Fig. 2 reports the degradation curves.

Degradation kinetics show significant variability among the different samples. Relatively slow SMZ degradation was observed in ultra-pure (Milli-Q) water, which represents the direct photolysis kinetics under the used irradiation device. Similar results were obtained in a lake sample (Candia) and in a sample from a freshwater aquaculture pond (Levaldigi), where SMZ direct photolysis would also be important. In contrast, significantly faster kinetics were observed in river (Po, Chao Phraya), lake (Avigliana), and especially in the brackish water (Thailand) samples.

In the latter cases, acceleration of SMZ photodegradation would likely be caused by indirect photochemistry. Indirect photoreactions of SMZ are in fact best highlighted when the direct photolysis is attenuated (Bahnmüller et al., 2014), as in the present experimental conditions ($\lambda > 340 \text{ nm}$). The brackish water sample had an elevated DOC value (almost $14 \text{ mg}_C L^{-1}$, see Table SM1), which is a condition where ${}^3CDOM^*$ -induced reactions are typically favored (McNeill and Canonica, 2016). To test this hypothesis, experiments of 2,4,6-trimethylphenol (TMP)

Fig. 2. Photodegradation time trends of SMZ spiked to the different natural water matrices, upon irradiation under the solar simulator equipped with a 340 nm cut-off filter. Note the break in the X-axis.

photodegradation were carried out in the natural water samples under study, in the same conditions used for SMZ. The TMP is an effective probe for $^3\text{CDOM}^*$, with which it reacts with a second-order reaction rate constant above $10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Al Housari et al., 2010).

The results (Table SM2) show that also TMP degradation was by far the fastest ($k'_{\text{TMP}} = 0.32 \text{ h}^{-1}$) in the brackish water sample, which suggests that triplet-sensitization processes were prominent in this water matrix. Interestingly, organic matter in coastal seawater (and especially in water affected by mariculture, as in the case of our brackish water sample) has been shown to possess high ability to photoproduce triplet states that were active in the degradation of the sulfonamide antibiotic sulfachloropyridazine (Guo et al., 2021). Furthermore, elevated ionic strength has been shown to inhibit triplet-state decay and thus enhance $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ -induced reactions (Parker et al., 2013), although this issue would be partially offset by the scavenging of $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ by halogenide ions (Carena et al., 2025). Still, a moderate level of salinity has been found to enhance the triplet-sensitized degradation of sulfadiazine, another sulfonamide antibiotic (Bai et al., 2021).

In order to further prove that triplet sensitization was involved in SMZ photodegradation, we carried out experiments with brackish water under nitrogen and oxygen atmospheres. To do so, we bubbled the gases inside the irradiation cells for 20 min prior to irradiation, through screw caps equipped with self-sealing silicone septa. The rationale is that $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ in aerated solution is mostly quenched by oxygen to partially yield $^1\text{O}_2$ (50 % yield, reaction (9); McNeill and Canonica, 2016), thus the $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ processes are enhanced and the $^1\text{O}_2$ ones inhibited if oxygen is removed.

Experimental results (Figure SM2) showed that SMZ photodegradation was faster without O_2 , which supports the hypothesis that $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ was involved in the process. Important reaction between SMZ and $^1\text{O}_2$ is also excluded, as already suggested by preliminary irradiation experiments (Fig. 1a).

The natural water samples were also subjected to further characterization by fluorescence (EEM, excitation-emission matrix) spectroscopy, to identify fluorescent organic matter components (see Figure SM3 for the EEM spectra) (Huguet et al., 2009; McKnight et al., 2001; Sciscenko et al., 2024; Zsolnay et al., 1999). Overall, EEM spectroscopy suggested the occurrence of a mixture of organic material from both autochthonous and allochthonous sources (see Text SM2).

When carrying out EEM peak identification according to Sciscenko et al. (2022), the Levaldigi, Avigliana lake, brackish water, and Chao Phraya River samples all showed the presence of humic-like substances. As far as protein-related material is concerned, tyrosine-like substances were detected in Candia Lake and Po River, while tryptophan-like substances were found in Levaldigi water only.

The PARAFAC analysis suggested the occurrence of two main components in the investigated samples, namely a humic-like one (component 1) and a protein-like one (component 2) (see Figure SM4a). Component 1 prevailed over component 2 in all the samples, with the single exception of Levaldigi (Figure SM4b). Interestingly, component 1 was prominent in the brackish water sample. Considering the ability of humic substances to photoproduce reactive triplet states (McNeill and Canonica, 2016), this finding further supports the type of photochemical reactivity we observed in the brackish-water sample.

It should be noted that our research focuses on photodegradation pathways, but SMZ elimination in aquaculture systems could also be influenced by simultaneous processes such as biodegradation and adsorption. In particular, sediments and biofilms in mariculture environments can contribute to sulfonamide antibiotics elimination through microbial transformation (Jing et al., 2025; Liang et al., 2021). These processes were not assessed in the present work, but they are components of the overall environmental fate of SMZ.

Further studies are necessary to investigate the collective effects of

photolysis, biodegradation, and adsorption under aquaculture conditions, as well as their relative role. Additional studies involving purified DOM isolates or DOM additions to ultra-pure water would be beneficial, to further address the sensitizing role of DOM under controlled conditions.

3.3. Photo-transformation products

During the irradiation experiments of SMZ in different conditions and with different water matrices, the formation of several transformation products (TPs) was detected. The identified TPs are summarized in Table SM3. In particular.

- The TP1 was formed under direct photolysis conditions and in the presence of nitrate (UV-B irradiation in both cases).
- The TP2 was only found upon irradiation of SMZ in the natural water samples (irradiation with $\lambda > 340 \text{ nm}$).
- The TP3 was found in experiments carried out under UV-B (direct photolysis, nitrate, nitrate + bicarbonate) and UV-A irradiation (CBBP).
- The SMZ isomer was found under UV-B irradiation (direct photolysis, nitrate, nitrate + bicarbonate).

These products were identified by LC-MS/MS, taking into consideration their masses, observed fragmentation patterns from databases (Massbank, <https://massbank.eu/MassBank/>), and literature findings.

The TP1 with m/z 99 is possibly generated from S-N bond cleavage. Considering its MS/MS spectrum, the loss of a -CHN group from the molecular ion (m/z 99) explains the formation of the product ion at m/z 72. This issue suggests that TP1 retains a small heterocyclic core, probably derived from the isoxazole ring or its immediate environment, which is in agreement with the findings of Hernández-Tenorio (2024). The detection of TP1 in our experiments can be compared with the results of Yang et al. (2017), who found it in the presence of $\bullet\text{OH}$ and $\text{CO}_3^{\bullet-}$ radicals, and with Alharbi et al. (2017), who detected TP1 in the direct photolysis of SMZ.

The TP2 with m/z 255 is consistent with the substitution of the amino group with a hydroxyl group. Looking at the MS/MS spectra, the signal at m/z 161 can be attributed to C-S bond breaking from the phenolic moiety. The product ions at m/z 157 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{S}$) and m/z 99 ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}$) can be attributed to fragments resulting from S-N break. Up to date, the presence of TP2 was only reported under photocatalytic conditions but not in the presence of real water matrices (Cao et al., 2021; Shen et al., 2022). The proposed formation of TP2 is based on its mass spectral profile and consistent formation under conditions favoring triplet-sensitized reactions (e.g., in the presence of DOM and under long-wavelength irradiation). While we speculate that TP2 is produced by a $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ -mediated transformation, the underlying mechanism remains theoretical. However, the hypothesis of a $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ -initiated transformation is supported by the fact that hydroxylation and oxidative pathways have been previously documented for sulfonamides and structurally comparable compounds in the presence of $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ (Li et al., 2015; McNeill & Canonica, 2016). Dedicated mechanistic studies will be necessary to definitively confirm the pathway leading to TP2.

The TP3 with m/z 84 may be formed through the rupture of the S-N bond and subsequent loss of the NH_2 group. The m/z 57 fragment can be attributed to ring opening with the detachment of the CHN moiety. In a previous study, Bui et al. (2022) have detected TP3 under photocatalytic oxidation conditions.

A species holding the same m/z ratio as the parent compound (m/z 254) was detected at lower retention time compared to SMZ. This SMZ isomer exhibits the formation of the same product ions already found from SMZ, namely: m/z 156 with the characteristic loss of the sulfonyl moiety, m/z 108 formed through joint losses of the sulfonyl moiety and a -SO group, and m/z 92 attributed to the cleavage of the C-S bond from the aniline moiety. An additional product ion at m/z 99 is observed,

possibly generated from S-N bond fragmentation as seen in TP1 (Alharbi et al., 2017; Hernández-Tenorio, 2024). In previous studies, Trovó et al. (2009), Yang et al. (2017), and Marín-García et al. (2022) also mentioned that SMZ isomerization occurred upon UV irradiation, where SMZ suffered a rearrangement of the isoxazole ring leading to the detected oxazole isomer.

Supplementary Figures SM5-SM8 show the temporal evolution of the detected TPs, and their interpretation can be found in Text SM3. In our experiments, it is remarkable that only TP2 was detected when natural water samples were irradiated at $\lambda > 340$ nm, under which conditions the direct photolysis of SMZ would be inhibited. In contrast, all the other TPs were detected when SMZ underwent UV (UV-A or UV-B) irradiation, under which conditions the direct photolysis process would be operational. Moreover, the same TPs were not detected upon irradiation of natural water samples, in which conditions the direct photolysis of SMZ was minimized. As far as TP2 is concerned, the fact that it was detected in the highest amount upon irradiation of brackish water (see Figure SM6), where triplet sensitization was particularly effective, but not with CBBP/UV-A, has two possible explanations: (i) CBBP is not representative of the triplet sensitizers occurring in brackish water, or (ii) TP2 is highly photolabile under UV-B and UV-A irradiation and/or in the presence of $^3\text{CBBP}^*$, which would explain why it was only detected upon irradiation with $\lambda > 340$ nm. Particularly, the high DOC and potential sensitizing capacity of brackish water environments might favor rapid formation of TP2 (see Figure SM6). While TP2 formation in freshwater was also observed, it occurred more slowly.

Interestingly, sulfonamide antibiotics with six-member heterocyclic rings have been found to undergo a process of SO_2 -group photoextrusion upon triplet sensitization (Boreen et al., 2005). We did not detect TPs arising from SO_2 loss from SMZ, but it should be considered that SMZ has somewhat different structure than the compounds studied by Boreen et al. (2005), because it has a five- (not six-) member heterocyclic ring.

3.4. Toxicity assessment of SMZ and its identified TPs

The ECOSAR results for SMZ, TP1, TP2, TP3, and the SMZ isomer are reported in Table SM4. The TP1 shows lower toxicity compared to SMZ for fish and daphnids but has slightly higher effects on green algae ($\text{EC}_{50} \sim 14 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$). The TP3 does not appear to be particularly toxic, and it would show lower acute and chronic toxicity than SMZ towards all target organisms. Additionally, the toxicity of the SMZ isomer would be comparable to that of the parent compound across all endpoints (Xu et al., 2022).

The TP2 appears to be of higher concern, due to its low LC_{50} and EC_{50} values, showing to a notable environmental risk among the detected TPs. According to Reuschenbach et al. (2008) and UNECE (2019), TP2 would be classified in the toxic class, in contrast with the other compounds that would be classified as not harmful. Therefore, conditions leading to the transformation of SMZ into TP2 have potential ecological implications, especially for fish and algae. It is interesting to observe that TP2 reached high concentration values upon irradiation in the brackish water sample, but it was also quickly removed by degradation (see Figure SM6). The TP2 is a phenolic compound. According to McNeill & Canonica (2016), the TP2 is expected to react fast by triplet sensitization due to its electron-rich aromatic structure, which facilitates energy and electron transfer processes. In the brackish water sample (high DOC and humic content), these conditions probably enhanced the formation of $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ species, accelerating the degradation of TP2. Moreover, TP2 was not detected in UV-B or UV-A irradiation experiments, suggesting it may be photolabile and supporting the hypothesis of fast photodegradation.

4. Conclusions

Sulfamethoxazole (SMZ) mostly absorbs sunlight in the UV-B region, which triggers its direct photolysis. Furthermore, SMZ also undergoes

degradation upon reaction with $\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$, and $^3\text{CDOM}^*$. The different photodegradation pathways could potentially lead to SMZ removal from surface-water environments with a time scale of a few days, and the direct photolysis would play an important role in shallow freshwaters. The direct photolysis of SMZ yields compounds that would be comparably toxic (TP1 and the SMZ isomer) or less toxic (TP3) than SMZ itself towards freshwater organisms.

In environments where SMZ direct photolysis is inhibited by the screening of short-wavelength sunlight, there is potential for indirect phototransformation to take on importance. In this work, we observed peculiarly fast indirect photodegradation of SMZ in a brackish-water sample from an aquaculture station, which contained high DOC and strong fluorescence signature by humic substances. By using 2,4,6-trimethylphenol as $^3\text{CDOM}^*$ probe, we could show that the brackish-water sample could induce very effective triplet-sensitization processes. In that sample we also observed high photoinduced generation of compound TP2, which arises from the transformation of the anilino moiety of SMZ into a phenolic group. The TP2 might be more toxic than SMZ towards fish and algae, although it might also be fast degraded. On this basis, matrices with high DOC and high photosensitization capacity would be very interesting for site-specific monitoring and risk assessment of SMZ.

The knowledge obtained in this study has implications for environmental protection and water quality. By taking into account the degradation of SMZ in real-life situations, the slower degradation rates, and the by-products observed under natural conditions, it can be ensured that the persistence and toxicity of SMZ in sunlit waters are not underestimated. The present findings are particularly relevant to antibiotic management, because understanding how SMZ photodegrades, especially in aquaculture ponds, can inform best practices in antibiotic use and wastewater treatment.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Manuel A. Andino-Enrriquez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Debora Fabbri:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Davide Vione:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Paola Calza:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

X The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the European Union under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) – Doctoral Network- IN2AQUAS (grant agreement No. 101119555) and by MSCA-Horizon 2020-RISE SusWater (grant agreement No. 101007578). The authors thank the Department of Science Service (DSS) of Bangkok, Thailand, for providing water samples and Iván Scisenko (Department of Chemistry, University of Torino) for help in the analysis and characterization of natural water samples by fluorescence spectroscopy. PC, DF, and DV acknowledge support from the Project CH4.0 under the MUR program "Dipartimenti di Eccellenza 2023–2027" (CUP: D13C22003520001). DV also acknowledges support by Next Generation EU – PNRR project GRINS (Growing Resilient, INclusive, and Sustainable), PE9 - spoke 6 (PE00000018, CUP: D13C22002160001).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2025.126947>.

[org/10.1016/j.envpol.2025.126947](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2025.126947).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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